

Intraperitoneal Stones Cause of Postcholecystectomy Syndrome : Case Report and Review of the Literature

Jenry Nataniel Orihuela Pedreros*¹, Judith Guadalupe Peña del Ángel ², Carla Ruby Beylan Vázquez ³, Maxim Alejandra Muñoz Gómez⁴, Jorge Luis López Villegas⁵, Jesús Armando Ruvalcaba Velázquez⁶

¹Fourth-year resident in General Surgery, Department of General Surgery, Health Services of Yucatán, “Dr. Agustín O’Horán” General Hospital, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico. Autonomous University of Yucatán.

²Third-year resident in Epidemiology, Department of Epidemiology, Health Services of Yucatán, “Lic Ignacio García Tellez” IMSS General Hospital, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico.

^{3,4,5}General Surgeon, attending physician in the General Surgery Department, Health Services of Yucatán, “Dr. Agustín O’Horán” General Hospital, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico.

⁶General Surgeon, Head of Services of General Surgery Department, Health Services of Yucatán, “Dr. Agustín O’Horán” General Hospital, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico.

ABSTRACT

Background: Postcholecystectomy syndrome due to abandoned intraperitoneal stones is a rare but significant complication of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. **Case:** A 52-year-old woman with a history of cholecystectomy 15 years ago, who presented pain in the right hypochondrium, nausea and vomiting. Imaging studies revealed intraperitoneal stones and scleroatrophic remnant gallbladder. **Intervention:** Laparoscopic reoperation was performed with extraction of two stones (one free intraperitoneal of 4×3 cm and another intravesicular of 5×3 cm) and completed cholecystectomy of the remaining gallbladder. **Result:** Successful procedure with no intraoperative complications. The patient had a favorable postoperative evolution with complete resolution of the symptoms. **Conclusion:** Laparoscopic management of postcholecystectomy syndrome due to residual stones is effective even in the presence of severe adhesions. Prevention by careful surgical technique and thorough washing during the initial cholecystectomy is essential.

KEYWORDS: laparoscopic cholecystectomy, postcholecystectomy syndrome, intraperitoneal liths, laparoscopic reoperation, residual stones.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
24 February 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Cholelithiasis is a common entity worldwide. In Mexico, approximately 20% of men and 40-50% of women suffer from cholelithiasis(1). It affects 10-15% of the population in Western countries and causes symptoms or complications in nearly 20% of cases(2). In terms of frequency, it represents the primary cause of hospital admission for digestive disease. Its prevalence is increasing as a consequence of greater life expectancy and the rising incidence of obesity and metabolic syndrome(3).

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy currently represents the gold standard for the treatment of gallbladder lithiasis, constituting one of the most frequent interventions in digestive surgery

worldwide(4,5). In Mexico, according to data from the General Directorate of Health Information (DGIS), between 180,000 and 220,000 cholecystectomies are performed annually, of which 85-90% are laparoscopic(6). In the United States, more than 750,000 cholecystectomies are performed annually(1).

Despite being considered a safe procedure, laparoscopic cholecystectomy may be associated with specific complications. Intraperitoneal spillage of gallstones occurs in approximately 5-40% of procedures(7), although complications secondary to this event are infrequent. However, when they occur, they may manifest as postcholecystectomy syndrome (PCS), characterized by a

Intraperitoneal Stones Cause of Postcholecystectomy Syndrome : Case Report and Review of the Literature

spectrum of gastrointestinal symptoms that can appear even years after the initial surgery(8). These can produce serous or purulent collections and may cause generalized peritonitis, depending on the size of the stones(9,10) and the degree of bacterial contamination(11). Large or pigmented stones have a higher probability of producing these complications(12,13). The literature reports that 10-30% of gallstones left intraperitoneally can cause late complications, including abscesses, intestinal obstruction, fistulas, and chronic abdominal pain(14). These complications may present both in the proximity of the subhepatic space and at distant sites, and their management frequently requires surgical reintervention(15). Various techniques and instruments are available for stone extraction: ligation or clips on the gallbladder wall(16), aspiration of small stones(17), Dormia baskets(18), retrieval bags(19), gloves or condoms(20).

CASE REPORT JUSTIFICATION

This case is relevant due to its presentation of an uncommon combination of free intraperitoneal gallstone and remnant sclerotic gallbladder with lithiasis, manifesting 15 years after the initial surgery. The late presentation and successful laparoscopic management despite severe adhesions provide valuable information for clinical practice.

Primary Objective

To describe the approach, diagnosis, and surgical management of postcholecystectomy syndrome due to intraperitoneal lithiasis at the secondary level of medical care.

Methodology: This is an observational, descriptive, retrospective, cross-sectional case study.

Patient: 52-year-old female, homemaker, married, with no history of chronic degenerative diseases. **Relevant Surgical History:** 2009: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy in Villahermosa, Tabasco (15 years ago) 2019: Multimodal treatment for cervical cancer stage IIIC. April 2019: Histopathological diagnosis, neoadjuvant chemotherapy (5 cycles), external beam radiotherapy (25 sessions), brachytherapy (3 sessions) June 2019: Radical oncologic surgery (total abdominal hysterectomy, bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy, omentectomy, appendectomy, peritoneal sampling, and pelvic lymphadenectomy).

Current status: Complete remission under medical oncology surveillance.

Current Clinical Presentation: December 2024: Onset of right upper quadrant pain associated with repeated nausea and vomiting of gastrointestinal content following ingestion of cholecystokinetic agents. A diagnostic workup was initiated.

Physical Examination: Alert and oriented patient with stable vital signs and no cardiopulmonary abnormalities. Abdomen with surgical scars in subxiphoid, right subcostal (anterior mammillary line), and supraumbilical regions; no evidence of hernias. Mild tenderness on deep palpation in right upper quadrant; Murphy's and Giordano's signs negative. Extremities intact, functional, with peripheral pulses present.

Initial Laboratory Findings: Complete blood count: WBC $7.5 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, neutrophils 78%, hemoglobin 13.3 g/dL, hematocrit 35%, platelets $288,000/\mu\text{L}$

Coagulation profile: PT 10.9 s, PTT 30.2 s, INR 0.99

Biochemistry: Glucose 111 mg/dL, creatinine 0.9 mg/dL, sodium 142 mEq/L, potassium 4.3 mEq/L, chloride 104 mEq/L

Hepatic profile: Total bilirubin 0.6 mg/dL (direct 0.1 mg/dL), AST 20 U/L, ALT 17 U/L, alkaline phosphatase 75 U/L

Pancreatic enzymes: Amylase 37.3 U/L, lipase 9 U/L

Tumor markers: CA 19-9: 6.90 U/mL

Other: CRP 1.27 mg/dL, LDH 165 U/L, cholesterol 143 mg/dL

Imaging Studies: Abdominal ultrasound: Distended gallbladder structure (60×27 mm) with multiple stones producing acoustic shadowing, gallbladder wall 3 mm in evaluable portion, common bile duct: 3.5 mm (normal), portal vein: 9 mm (normal).

Contrast-enhanced abdominal computed tomography: Liver: Preserved morphology and size, simple cyst in segment IV.

Biliary tract: Normal caliber intra- and extrahepatic ducts

Key finding: Moderately distended gallbladder structure with: Calcified wall contours, two intraluminal stones (6 mm and 3 mm, 57 HU attenuation), fluid-fluid level consistent with biliary sludge. Surgical clips: Y-shaped hyperdense image at cystic duct level (1375 HU) and another on hepatic capsule (segment VI). Free stone: Encapsulated hyperdense image in subhepatic space. (concordant with medical history).

Figure 1: Subhepatic calculus

Figure 2: Gallbladder bed calculus

Surgical Decision: Scheduled laparoscopic reintervention

Operative Results: Approach: Laparoscopic via Veress technique

Duration: 150 minutes

Surgical Technique:

Pneumoperitoneum: Established with CO₂ at 12-15 mmHg and initial port 12 mm umbilical for optical trocar

Diagnostic laparoscopy: Identification of severe adhesive syndrome in right upper quadrant

Adhesiolysis: Careful liberation until exposure of right hepatic border

Intraoperative findings: Encapsulated free stone measuring 4×3 cm in subhepatic space, Remnant sclerotic gallbladder (Parkland V) with intraluminal calculus, Dense fibrous adhesions to hepatic bed additional ports: Two 5 mm

ports (right anterior and mid-axillary lines) free stone liberation: Careful dissection with structure preservation
Gallbladder approach: "Open book" anterior wall opening
Intravesicular stone extraction: 5×3 cm calculus occupying entire lumen.

Completed cholecystectomy: Identification and clipping of cystic duct with two 5 mm green Hem-o-lok® clips, Hepatocystic bed dissection, Hemostatic control with electrocautery

Specimen extraction: Both stones and gallbladder remnants in extraction bag, the procedure was completed without incidents or intraoperative complications

Postoperative Course

Drainage: Jackson-Pratt in foramen of Winslow

Hospitalization:

Duration: 48 hours, gradual progression from clear liquids, analgesia multimodal with adequate pain control, drainage scant serosanguineous output, removed at 48 hours

Follow-up: 7-day control: Surgical wounds in good condition, 30-day control: Asymptomatic, return to activities

DISCUSSION

Relevant Clinical Aspects

Postcholecystectomy syndrome due to residual gallstones represents an infrequent but clinically significant late complication. In this case, the late presentation (15 years postoperatively) and the combination of free intraperitoneal stone with remnant sclerotic gallbladder constitute uncommon findings in the literature.

Diagnostic Analysis

The initial discrepancy between surgical history and ultrasonographic findings suggestive of present gallbladder highlighted the importance of computed tomography as the definitive study. This case illustrates how a documented "complete" cholecystectomy may actually correspond to an unrecognized subtotal cholecystectomy, a situation that can occur under conditions of severe inflammation or complex anatomy(21).

Technical Considerations

Laparoscopic management proved feasible and effective despite severe adhesions, consistent with reports indicating viability of the minimally invasive approach in 85-90% of cases with dense adhesions(22). Careful adhesiolysis technique and systematic structure identification were fundamental to procedural success(23).

Comparison with Literature

Previous studies report that 10-30% of gallstones abandoned during laparoscopic cholecystectomy may cause late complications(24). The most frequent manifestations include subhepatic abscesses, intestinal obstruction, fistulas, and chronic abdominal pain(25,26). In our institutional series, this represents the first case of remnant sclerotic gallbladder associated with free intraperitoneal stone.

Medicolegal Implications

This case highlights the importance of detailed surgical documentation and adequate follow-up of patients with gallbladder perforation during cholecystectomy. The lack of documentation regarding the subtotal nature of the initial cholecystectomy complicated differential diagnosis and delayed appropriate management.

LIMITATIONS

This report presents the inherent limitations of a single case study, including the impossibility of establishing definitive causal relationships and lack of long-term follow-up. Additionally, the absence of detailed documentation of the initial surgery limited analysis of predisposing factors.

CONCLUSIONS

Management of postcholecystectomy syndrome due to residual stones requires a multidisciplinary approach including early diagnostic suspicion, appropriate imaging studies, and surgical reintervention when indicated. Laparoscopic approach proved effective in this complex case, with a reported success rate of 89-90% in the literature.

Prevention remains the most important strategy, emphasizing careful surgical technique, meticulous stone extraction, and thorough peritoneal cavity lavage in cases of gallbladder perforation. This case demonstrates that even exceptional late complications can be successfully resolved with appropriate surgical management.

Timely diagnosis and multidisciplinary treatment resulted in favorable clinical evolution, with complete symptom resolution and excellent functional prognosis. The patient continues in outpatient follow-up without evidence of additional complications.

Conflict of Interest: There were no conflicts of interest in this work.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Intraoperative Prevention: Perform thorough peritoneal cavity lavage in any gallbladder perforation during laparoscopic cholecystectomy, ensuring extraction of all gallstones to prevent subsequent migration. Document in

Intraperitoneal Stones Cause of Postcholecystectomy Syndrome : Case Report and Review of the Literature

detail in the operative report the presence of perforations, number of stones recovered, and lavage technique employed. Timely Diagnosis: Include postcholecystectomy syndrome due to residual stones in the differential diagnosis of patients with persistent or recurrent abdominal pain post-cholecystectomy, regardless of time elapsed since initial surgery. Prioritize imaging studies (abdominal ultrasound, computed tomography, or magnetic resonance imaging) in symptomatic patients, especially if there is a history of gallbladder perforation or subtotal cholecystectomy.

Surgical Management: Consider laparoscopic approach as first option for residual stone extraction, even in cases with severe adhesions, given its efficacy and lower morbidity compared to open surgery. Evaluate the presence of gallbladder remnants or residual biliary structures during reintervention, completing cholecystectomy if necessary.

Follow-up: Establish postoperative controls with clinical evaluation and imaging studies in high-risk patients (e.g., previous intraoperative perforation, multiple gallstones). Promote standardization of institutional follow-up protocols to detect late complications.

Education and Training: Incorporate into surgical training strategies to minimize the risk of leaving gallstones behind, emphasizing safe dissection techniques and management of gallbladder perforations. Promote dissemination of case reports and clinical guidelines among surgical teams to improve awareness of this complication.

Acknowledgments: Special thanks to Hospital General "Agustín O'Horán" and the Faculty of Medicine of the "Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán".

Funding: None.

Conflict of interest: None declared.

Ethical considerations: The patient was fully informed about the diagnosis, procedures, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures as well as for publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

REFERENCES

- I. Santos Macedo GN, López Viurquiz U de J, Sánchez Servín CE. Reporte de Caso: Síndrome Postcolecistectomía Secundario a Remanente de Muñón Vesicular. *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*. 2024;7(6).
- II. Pavón CJC, Bermejo MF, Artero SM, Amo Olea E del. Absceso subhepático como complicación tardía de un cálculo intraperitoneal abandonado tras una colecistectomía laparoscópica. *Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2004;27(10).
- III. Corpechot C, Pariente A. Litiasis biliar. *EMC - Tratado de Medicina*. 2024;28(1).
- IV. Jaunoo SS, Mohandas S, Almond LM. Postcholecystectomy syndrome (PCS). Vol. 8, *International Journal of Surgery*. 2010.
- V. Burckhardt O, Peisl S, Rouiller B, Colinet E, Egger B. Length of the Remnant Cystic Duct and Bile Duct Stone Recurrence: a Case–Control Study. *Journal of Gastrointestinal Surgery*. 2023;27(6).
- VI. Dirección General de Información en Salud. Anuario de Morbilidad Hospitalaria. México. Mexico; 2023.
- VII. Lamberts MP, Lugtenberg M, Rovers MM, Roukema AJ, Drenth JPH, Westert GP, et al. Persistent and de novo symptoms after cholecystectomy: A systematic review of cholecystectomy effectiveness. Vol. 27, *Surgical Endoscopy*. 2013.
- VIII. Sathesh-Kumar T, Saklani AP, Vinayagam R, Blackett RL. Spilled gall stones during laparoscopic cholecystectomy: A review of the literature. Vol. 80, *Postgraduate Medical Journal*. 2004. p. 77–9.
- IX. Diez J, Arozamena CJ, Ferraina P, Franci JM, Ferreres A, Lardies JM, et al. Relation between postoperative infections and gallbladder bile leakage during laparoscopic cholecystectomies. *Surg Endosc*. 1996;10(5).
- X. Stewart L, Smith AL, Pellegrini CA, Motson RW, Way LW. Pigment gallstones form as a composite of bacterial microcolonies and pigment solids. *Ann Surg*. 1987;206(3).
- XI. Humm GL, Peckham-Cooper A, Chang J, Fernandes R, Gomez NF, Mohan H, et al. Surgical experience and identification of errors in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *British Journal of Surgery*. 2023;110(11).
- XII. Nooghabi AJ, Hassanpour M, Jangjoo A. Consequences of Lost Gallstones during Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy: A Review Article. Vol. 26, *Surgical Laparoscopy, Endoscopy and Percutaneous Techniques*. 2016.
- XIII. Habib E, Elhadad A. Digestive complications of gallstones lost during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *HPB*. 2003;5(2).
- XIV. Castellón-Pavón CJ, Morales-Artero S, Martínez-Pozuelo A, Valderrábano-González S. Complicaciones por cálculos y clips intraabdominales abandonados durante una colecistectomía laparoscópica. Vol. 84, *Cirugía Española*. 2008.
- XV. Strasberg SM, Hertl M, Soper NJ. An analysis of the problem of biliary injury during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Vol. 180, *Journal of the American College of Surgeons*. 1995.
- XVI. Soper NJ, Dunnegan DL. Does intraoperative gallbladder perforation influence the early outcome

Intraperitoneal Stones Cause of Postcholecystectomy Syndrome : Case Report and Review of the Literature

- of laparoscopic cholecystectomy? *Surg Laparosc Endosc.* 1991;1(3).
- XVII. Schäfer M, Suter C, Klaiber C, Wehrli H, Frei E, Krähenbühl L. Spilled gallstones after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: A relevant problem? A retrospective analysis of 10,174 laparoscopic cholecystectomies. *Surg Endosc.* 1998;12(4).
- XVIII. Welch NT, Hinder RA, Ciurej T, Bacon N. Laparoscopic capture of “escaped” gallstones. *Surg Laparosc Endosc.* 1991;1(1).
- XIX. Singh K, Wang ML, Ofori E, Widmann W, Alemi A, Nakaska M. Gallstone abscess as a result of dropped gallstones during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Int J Surg Case Rep.* 2012;3(12).
- XX. Diez J, Arozamena C, Gutierrez L, Bracco J, Mon A, Sanchez Almeyra R, et al. Lost stones during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *HPB Surgery.* 1998;11(2).
- XXI. Sabiston DC TCM. *Sabiston Textbook of Surgery: The Biological Basis of Modern Surgical Practice.* 21st ed. 21st ed. Vol. 1. 2022.
- XXII. Fletcher R, Cortina CS, Kornfield H, Varelas A, Li R, Veenstra B, et al. Bile duct injuries: a contemporary survey of surgeon attitudes and experiences. *Surg Endosc.* 2020;34(7).
- XXIII. Upchurch CP, Haas NL, Magnone G, Compton J. Symptomatic Cholelithiasis of a Remnant Gallbladder after Open Cholecystectomy. *Journal of Emergency Medicine.* 2018;55(3).
- XXIV. Gupta V, Jain G. Safe laparoscopic cholecystectomy: Adoption of universal culture of safety in cholecystectomy. *World J Gastrointest Surg.* 2019 Feb 27;11(2):62–84.
- XXV. 10. Barbier L HC. Complicaciones de la colecistectomía. *EMC - Técnicas Quirúrgicas - Aparato Digestivo.* . 2023. 1–13 p.
- XXVI. Alexander HC, Bartlett AS, Wells CI, Hannam JA, Moore MR, Poole GH, et al. Reporting of complications after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a systematic review. Vol. 20, *HPB.* 2018.